

CHC MODEL OF COGNITIVE ABILITIES- BASED EDUCATIONAL THERAPY

PRESENTED BY

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Dr Chia Kok Hwee, Managing Principal Diagnostician and Therapist

- Singaporean, obtained a **Doctorate in Education** from the **University of Western Australia**.
- Triple Board Certified (Practising licences in educational diagnostic & therapy, reading therapy and special education) of the International Association of Counselors and Therapists (**IACT**), Association of Educational Therapists (**AET**) and American Association of Special Needs Professionals (**AASEP**), Honorary Fellow of the Reading Specialists' Association Singapore (HonFRSAS), Registered Reading Therapist.
- He has been practising for almost 30 years since 1997.
- He was awarded Omega Gamma Chi Award by the National Association of Special Education Teachers, USA (**NASET**), in 2012.
- He received a letter of appreciation in 2017 from the Minister of Social and Family Development (**MSF**), Singapore.
- He received two Certificates of Recognition in 2009 and 2014 from the AET for his contribution as a study group leader in Singapore
- He received a letter of good standing and commendation from IACT in 2023.
- Since 2008, he has written prolifically and contributed research papers to SCI and Scopus-accredited journals alongside the authoring of academic publications.

**World Health
Organization**

Comorbidities include:

- (i) **Neurodevelopmental disorders** (ASD, ADHD, dyslexia)
- (ii) **Psychiatric disorders** (anxiety, depression, bipolar, OCD etc)
- (iii) **Learning disorders & disabilities** in cognitive skills (imagination, reasoning, creativity, cognitive flexibility, organisation, self management, time management etc)

**LEARNING
DISORDERS**

ASD

About **2% to 2.5%** are diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder. It is a neurological disorder. ASD children faces social and communication challenges.

1

ADHD

About **2%** of children are diagnosed with Attention Deficit/ Hyperactive Disorder. ADHD affect academic achievement, resulting in poorer acquisition of skills. 40% of people suffering from ADHD has ODD.

2

Language Disorder

About **5%**. This covers dyslexia and dyspraxia. Poorer language and communication skills may lead to selective mutism and social phobias.

3

Depression Disorder

About **2% to 4%** in children and adolescents. More women are affected by depression than men. Depression can lead to suicide. Recent stressors arising out of Covid increase the prevalence rate by 25%.

4

8 *Others*

Many others such as dysmorphic disorder, eating disorder, bipolar disorder, post traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), obsessive compulsive disorder are commonly heard disorders and may comorbid with others.

7 *ODD*

Oppositional Defiant Disorder affects about **2% to 5%** of the children and adolescents. It declines with increasing age. Severe cases may lead to conduct disorder or which shows ongoing pattern of aggression or resentment towards others and violations of rules.

6 *Dyscalculia*

Between **5% to 7%** of elementary children suffer from dyscalculia. This causes difficulty in arithmetical calculations leading to weak academic performance.

5 *Anxiety Disorder*

About **12.5%** of adolescents may have anxiety disorder. Counseling may reduce the level. Aggravation may lead to depression.

AGE OF ONSET OF VARIED DISORDERS

The age of psychological disorders' onset and suicidal rates decline in tandem.

13 Disability Categories as listed by the IDEA 2004.

When necessary, **Merlion Paediatric Therapy** provides the a comprehensive analysis based on the hierarchy of abilities and skills being assessed/evaluated to understand the changing pattern of strengths and weaknesses of the learning disorder or disability of the child concerned.

What is Educational Therapy (EdTx)?

EdTx is a specialized form of support designed for individuals with learning challenges, including those with (i) learning disorders, (ii) learning disabilities, (iii) learning difficulties, (iv) learning dysfunctions and (v) learning differences.

Educational therapists (ETs) are highly trained professionals who combine educational and therapeutic approaches to address various academic, social, emotional, and behavioral issues that impede learning.

Since **1986**, World Health Organisation (**WHO**) recognises **Educational Therapy** and classifies under the *diagnostic code 93.82* in **International Classification of Diseases**.

Educational therapy includes 3 main domains:

1. Non-pharmacological
2. Psychoeducational Diagnostic
3. Treatment: 3 areas
 - (i) Intervention
 - (ii) Rehabilitation
 - (iii) Management

国家医保信息业务编码标准数据库动态维护

ICD-10医保2.0版

ICD-9-CM3医保2.0版

点击下载PDF (MD5:612122a835bbdb5eec7087354993381)

关闭

- 89 会谈、评估、会诊和检查
- 90 显微镜检查-I
- 91 显微镜检查-II
- 92 核医学
- 93 物理治疗、呼吸治疗、康复和相关操
 - 93.0 诊断性物理治疗
 - 93.1 物理治疗运动训练
 - 93.2 其他物理治疗的肌肉骨骼手法操
 - 93.3 其他物理治疗的治疗性操作
 - 93.4 骨骼牵引和其他牵引
 - 93.5 其他制动术、压迫和伤口维护
 - 93.6 整骨推拿疗法
 - 93.7 语言和阅读康复和盲人康复
 - 93.8 其他康复治疗**
 - 93.9 呼吸治疗
- 94 与精神有关的操作
- 95 眼科和耳科诊断和治疗

其他康复治疗

93.81 娱乐治疗

93.8100 娱乐治疗

93.82 教育治疗

93.8200 教育治疗

93.83 职业治疗

+ 93.8300 职业治疗

93.8301 作业疗法

93.84 音乐治疗

93.8400 音乐治疗

93.85 职业康复

93.8500 职业康复

HIERARCHY OF ABILITIES AND SKILLS (CHIA, 2008, 2010)

A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO DIAGNOSTIC EVALUATION

Merlion Paediatric Therapy partners with hospitals and professional specialists of multi-disciplinary fields to further verify our psychoeducational diagnostic evaluation results.

PERIODIC TABLE OF HUMAN COGNITIVE ABILITIES

- Since **1940s**, research on CHC had already started, and the **first table** was devised in **2004**.
- It is the most complete periodic table of the human cognitive abilities to date.
- It has always been **referenced by IACT**.

- Cognitive-related abilities
- Conative-related abilities
- Affective-related abilities
- Sensory-related abilities

Gf-Fluid reasoning

- **I-Induction**
- **RG-General sequential reasoning**
- **RQ-Quantitative reasoning**
- *RE-Reasoning speed*
- *RP-Piagetian reasoning*

Gwm-Short-term working memory

- **Wa-Auditory short-term storage**
- **Wv-Visual-spatial short-term storage**
- **AC-Attentional control**
- **Wc-Working memory capacity**

Gl-Learning efficiency

- **MA-Associative memory**
- **MM-Meaningful memory**
- **M6-Free recall memory**

Gv-Visual processing

- **Vz-Visualization**
- **SR-Speeded rotation**
- **IM-Imagery**
- **CF-Flexibility of closure**
- **CS-Closure speed**
- **MV-Visual memory**
- **SS-Spatial scanning**
- **PI-Serial perceptual integration**
- **LE-Length estimation**
- **IL-Perceptual illusions**
- **PN-Perceptual alternations**
- **P-Perceptual speed ***

Ga-Auditory processing

- **PC-Phonetic coding**
- **US-Speech sound discrimination**
- **UR-Res. to auditory stim. dist.**
- **U8-Maint. & judging rhythm**
- **UM-Memory for sound patterns**
- **U1/U9-Musical discrimination & judgement**
- **UP-Absolute pitch**
- **UL-Sound localization**

Gc-Comprehension-knowledge

- **LD-Language development ***
- **VL-Lexical knowledge**
- **K0-General (verbal) information**
- **LS-Listening ability**
- **CM-Communication ability**
- **MY-Grammatical sensitivity**

Gkn-Domain-specific knowledge

- **K1-General science information**
- **K2-Knowledge of culture**
- **MK-Mechanical knowledge**
- **KL-Foreign language proficiency**
- **KF-Knowledge of signing**
- **LP-Skill in lip reading**

Grw-Reading and writing

- **RC-Reading comprehension**
- **RD-Reading decoding**
- **RS-Reading speed**
- **WA-Writing ability**
- **SG-Spelling ability**
- **EU-English usage**
- **WS-Writing speed**

Gq-Quantitative knowledge

- **KM-Mathematical knowledge**
- **A3-Mathematical achievement**

Gr-Retrieval fluency

- **FI-Ideational fluency**
- **FE-Expressional fluency**
- **FA-Associational fluency**
- **SP-Sensitivity to problems**
- **FO-Originality/creativity**
- **LA-Speed of lexical access ***
- **NA-Naming facility**
- **FW-Word fluency**
- **FF-Figural fluency**
- **FX-Figural flexibility**

Definitions can be found at:
<https://tinyurl.com/y8555sjh>

Gs-Processing speed

- **P-Perceptual speed ***
- **Ps-Perceptual speed-search**
- **Pc-Perceptual speed-compare**
- **N-Number facility**
- **RS-Reading speed**
- **WS-Writing speed**

Gt-Reaction and decision speed

- **R1-Simple reaction time**
- **R2-Choice reaction time**
- **IT-Inspection time**
- **R4-Semantic processing speed**
- **R7-Mental comparison speed**

Gps-Psychomotor speed

- **R3-Speed of limb movement**
- **WS-Writing speed**
- **PT-Speed of articulation**
- **MT-Movement time**

Gp-Psychomotor abilities

- **P1-Manual dexterity**
- **P2-Finger dexterity**
- **P3-Static strength**
- **P4-Gross body equilibrium**
- **P6-Multilimb coordination**
- **P7-Arm-hand steadiness**
- **P8-Control precision**
- **A1-Aiming**

Go-Olfactory abilities

- **OM-Olfactory memory**

Gh-Tactile abilities

- (Currently no well-supported abilities)

Gk-Kinesthetic abilities

- (Currently no well-supported abilities)

Gei-Emotional intelligence

- **Ep-Emotion perception**
- **Ek-Emotion knowledge**
- **Em-Emotion management**
- **Eu-Emotion utilization**

Narrow abilities with **bold font** = major ability; regular font = minor ability. If all factor codes are regular font under a broad ability = insufficient data to classify as major or minor (Schneider & McGrew, 2018)

Italic narrow factor code font designates "tentative" abilities

* = intermediate stratum abilities

Broad ability color codes**

- **Blue** – Intelligence-as-Process
- **Gray** – Intelligence-as-Knowledge
- **Green** – Intelligence-as-Process (speed/fluency)
- **Red** = other tentatively identified broad abilities

** First three as per Ackerman et al.'s PPIK model of intelligence

Source: Schneider, W. J., & McGrew, K. S. (2018). The Cattell-Horn-Carroll Theory of Cognitive Abilities. In D. P. Flanagan & Erin M. McDonough (Eds.), *Contemporary intellectual assessment: Theories, tests and issues* (4th ed.,) New York: Guilford Press.

Merlion Paediatric Therapy Clinic uses it for

1. Comprehensive PDA (**9hrs**)
2. Prepares intervention education plan (IEP) (**20 sessions**)
3. Verifiable with **fMRI results and genetics karyotype** on various disorders the child has.

Cattell-Horn-Carroll Theory of Cognitive Abilities

Educational Diagnostician

chc theory Cattell-Horn-Carroll Theory of Cognitive Abilities

Educational Therapist

chc theory applied to intervention

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME

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